

EFFECTS OF RADIATION ON InP CELLS EPITAXIALLY GROWN
ON Si AND GaAs SUBSTRATES

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ABSTRACT

The properties of heteroepitaxial InP cells were determined both before and after 10 MeV proton irradiations. Numerical values, obtained for the diffusion and recombination components of the reverse saturation currents, were found to be consistent with the distribution of dislocations. The radiation resistance of the heteroepitaxial cells was significantly greater than that observed for n/p homoepitaxial Inp cells. The carrier removal rate, obtained by C-V measurements, was $1.8 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for 10 MeV protons compared with 2.2 cm^{-1} for 1 MeV electrons. The high carrier removal rate was found to have no significant effect on the cell's series resistance. It was concluded that the heteroepitaxial cell performance is dominated by the high dislocation density attributable to lattice constant mismatch.

INTRODUCTION

Historically, 1984 marked a turning point in InP solar cell research. Prior to that year, no radiation damage results had been reported for these cells. Hence there was no indication of their potential importance as a spacecraft power source. In 1984, Yamaguchi and his coworkers found that InP solar cells were significantly more radiation resistant than either Si or GaAs under 1 MeV electron irradiation (1). This was followed, in 1985, by similar results obtained after 10 MeV proton irradiations (2). These investigations, together with subsequent annealing and temperature dependency studies, showed that InP solar cells were indeed strong candidates for use in degrading space radiation environments (3,4). To date, AMO efficiencies exceeding 19% are routinely obtained for 4 cm^2 InP cells and a small module has shown no degradation after almost three years in orbit (5,6). In addition a Japanese lunar orbiting satellite, powered by InP cells, was successfully launched in early 1990 (7). Despite these successes, the high cost of InP substrates presents a potential barrier toward widespread use of these cells in

space. This has served as motivation for recent activity aimed at processing cells from thin layers of Inp epitaxially deposited on cheaper, sturdier substrates (8,9,10). In the present case, we report on the pre and post irradiation properties of the initial cells produced in the U.S. under this program (9).

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The heteroepitaxial InP cells were processed, by OMCVD, at the Spire corporation, during a six months feasibility study under contract to NASA Lewis. The cells, in the n^+pp^+ configuration, were deposited to a thickness of 4 micrometers on a thick GaAs Substrate (InP/GaAs). A similar cell was deposited on a thin GaAs buffer layer which had previously been deposited on a thick Si substrate (InP/GaAs/Si). Additional details can be found in reference 9. The cells were irradiated by 10 MeV protons in the Lewis cyclotron. Cell performance measurements were carried out using a Xenon arc solar simulator and a flight calibrated InP standard solar cell. Capacitance-voltage measurements were performed both, before and after irradiation, in order to determine base majority carrier concentrations at the edge of the depletion region. Measurements of Isc and Voc, at varying light intensities, were obtained in order to determine the diffusion and recombination components of the the cell's reverse saturation currents. These were also combined with dark current measurements to determine series resistances.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pre-irradiation cell performance parameters are shown in Table I, together with predicted values based on the model proposed by Yamaguchi, et al (8). The low efficiencies are due to the high dislocation densities ($3-8 \times 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-2}$) caused essentially by lattice constant misfit (11). In fact, a reduction in dislocation density, by several orders of magnitude, is required in order to reach efficiencies

approaching 20%. Obviously, additional transition layers are required between the InP film and substrate in order to reduce dislocation densities. This has been demonstrated by Wanlass who achieved an AMO efficiency of 13.7% with InP cells using a GaAs substrate with intervening layers of $\text{Ga}_x\text{In}_{1-x}\text{As}$ (10). This latter semiconductor, with $x=0.47$, is lattice matched to InP.

The reduced efficiency of the present InP/GaAs/Si cell is attributed to a high series resistance. This is qualitatively illustrated in figure 1 where the I-V curves of the present heteroepitaxial cells are compared to a reasonably good homoepitaxial InP cell. In fact, the series resistance of the InP/GaAs/Si cell was 4.75 ohm cm^2 compared with 0.8 ohm cm^2 for the InP/GaAs cell and 0.44 ohm cm^2 for the homoepitaxial cell. The high series resistance of the InP/GaAs/Si cell originates from the necessity to short out a reverse diode caused by diffusion of silicon into GaAs at the high temperature (1000 °C) used in forming the buffer layer. This is accomplished by shorting out the reverse diode in regions outside of the cell's active area (9). This creates a high resistance path for holes travelling to the back contact (9).

The diffusion and recombination parameters, of the cell's dark current, are shown in table II. These are obtained from the I_{sc} -Voc data using the diode equation. In the table, J_{01} and J_{02} are the diffusion and recombination components respectively. The results for the present cells are compared, in the table, to data previously obtained for a homoepitaxial cell processed by OMCVD. Compared to the latter cell, J_{01} and J_{02} are significantly greater for the homoepitaxial cells, the greatest difference occurring in the diffusion component. The differences between the homoepitaxial and heteroepitaxial cells is largely due to the high dislocation densities in the latter cell types. Transmission electron microscopy of the present cell structures, indicates that the dislocation density is greatest at the semiconductor interfaces, decreasing markedly as one progresses toward the cell junction (9,11). Thus, J_{02} which is due to recombination in the cell's depletion region, is affected by a relatively low dislocation density, compared to J_{01} , which is affected largely by dislocations in the cell's base region. Hence, comparing the homoepitaxial and heteroepitaxial cells a much smaller difference occurs in the recombination component J_{02} . This result is consistent with the observed dislocation density distribution in the present cells.

A relatively small decrease in cell maximum power, under 10 MeV proton irradiation, is indicated in figure 2. A similar result applies to the remaining cell parameters (Table III).

Comparison of the present cells with the normalized efficiencies of an n/p homoepitaxial cell, in figure 3, indicates that the radiation resistance of the present cells is significantly greater than that of the homoepitaxial cell under 10 MeV proton irradiations. The normalized spectral response at long and short wavelength, shown in figure 4, indicates an anomalously low value for the short wavelength component. It is noted that, at the shorter wavelength, light absorption is essentially complete at the edge of the depletion region while for the longer wavelength only 25% of the light is absorbed in the cell's emitter and depletion regions. These effects are attributed to a low pre-irradiation minority carrier diffusion length (~ 0.2 micrometers), due to the relatively high dislocation densities in the present cells.

Carrier removal, by 10 MeV protons, was determined by plots of $1/C^2$ vs V , a typical post irradiation plot being shown in figure 5. After irradiation to a fluence of $1.1 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, the cell's p-base carrier concentration decreased markedly from the pre-irradiation value of $3 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ to a post irradiation value of $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The effect of carrier removal on cell series resistance was determined using the relation,

$$\Delta R_s = (L/Aq) \left(\frac{1}{p\mu_p} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\rho} - \frac{1}{(\rho\mu_p)_0} \right) \quad (1)$$

where L is the cell's p-base length, A is cell area, and the subscripts 0 and ρ denote pre and post-irradiation values respectively. With $L=3$ micrometers, $A=0.25 \text{ cm}^2$ and 150 and 170 cm^2 $V^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ for the post and pre-irradiation mobilities, respectively, it turns out that $R_s = 0.003$ ohms. Hence carrier removal has a negligible effect on series resistance.

The present data yields a carrier removal rate of $1.8 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This is compared to a carrier removal rate of 2.2 cm^{-1} for 1 MeV electrons, as obtained from the data of Yamaguchi, et al (12). The difference is due to the higher proton energies and possibly the tendency of protons to form defect clusters. The basic mechanism of carrier removal is unclear for both proton and electron irradiations. This is traceable to uncertainties in defect identification. For example; considering electron irradiations, the composition of the major radiation induced defect in p-type InP, labeled H4, has not been completely resolved. It has been suggested, using DLTS, that this defect is either a phosphorus vacancy or interstitial complexed with a shallow acceptor (13). On the other hand, Yamaguchi, et al, after electron irradiation, suggest that H4 is composed of a phosphorus vacancy and interstitial, both positively charged (14). The latter identification yields a faint clue to the nature of a carrier compensating mechanism which could contribute to a net decrease in

base carrier concentration. There have been no similar results for proton irradiations. Hence, the basic mechanism of carrier removal is uncertain in both cases.

CONCLUSION

The efficiencies of the present cells are admittedly low. However, the recent achievement of 13.7% AMO efficiencies using a GaAs substrate, demonstrates the marked improvement that can be attained using more appropriate transition layers. Assuming a solution of the problem associated with silicon autodoping, the same technique should ultimately result in much higher efficiencies for InP cells which use silicon as a substrate. In any event, it is concluded from the present results, that:

1. Dislocations tend to dominate the pre and post-irradiation performance of the present heteroepitaxial cells.
2. A high value of series resistance is the major factor in the reduced performance of the InP/GaAs/Si cell.
3. Considering reverse saturation currents, the values obtained for the diffusion and recombination components, are consistent with the observed dislocation distributions.
4. The radiation resistance of the present cells is significantly greater than that observed for n/p homoepitaxial Inp cells.
5. Carrier removal, due to 10 MeV protons, has a negligible effect on series resistance.
6. The basic mechanism of carrier removal is uncertain for both electron and proton irradiations.

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Table I. Measured and predicted pre-irradiation cell parameters				
Cell	J_{sc} ma/cm ²	V_{oc} mv	FF %	Efficiency %
InP/GaAs ^a	26.6±.7	667±4	69±1	8.9±.1
InP/GaAs/Si ^a	25.8±.3	642±4	57.7±1	6.95±.1
predicted ^b	29.6	600	77	9.9
^a Average 8 cells				
^b $N_D=3 \times 10^{18}/\text{cm}^2$, $p=3 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, 5% front contact coverage				

Table II. Diffusion and recombination parameters				
Cell	A ₁	A ₂	J_{01} A/cm ²	J_{02} A/cm
InP (OMCVD)	1.03	2.24	1.4×10^{-16}	4.1×10^{-9}
InP/GaAs	1.27	2.12	6.6×10^{-11}	1×10^{-7}
InP/GaAs/Si	1.26	2.15	1.7×10^{-10}	1.5×10^{-7}

Table III. Normalized Cell Parameters at High Fluence $\phi = 1.1 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$				
Cell	$J_{sc\phi}/J_{sc0}$	$V_{oc\phi}/V_{oc0}$	$FF\phi/FF_0$	$\eta\phi/\eta_0$
InP/GaAs/Si	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.91
InP/GaAs	0.98	0.97	0.96	0.91

FIGURE 1 - I-V CURVES-HETEROEPITAXIAL AND HOMOEPITAXIAL INP CELLS

FIGURE 2 - CELL MAXIMUM POWER VS 10 MeV PROTON FLUENCE

FIGURE 3 - COMPARISON OF INP/GAAS AND n/p INP AFTER 10 MeV PROTON IRRADIATION

FIGURE 4 - NORMALIZED SPECTRAL RESPONSE OF HETERO-EPITAXIAL CELL AT LONG AND SHORT WAVELENGTHS

FIGURE 5 - $1/c^2$ VS V OF HETEROEPITAXIAL CELL AFTER IRRADIATION